

Structural and Photovoltaic Enhancements in Cu-Doped Sb₂S₃ Thin Films via Chemical Bath Deposition

İpek BALNAN ^{1*}

¹ Sivas University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Department of Engineering Fundamental Sciences, Sivas

*Corresponding author: balnanipek@sivas.edu.tr

Received: 20.07.2025

Accepted: 02.09.2025

Abstract

Antimony sulfide (Sb₂S₃) is a promising absorber for low-cost optoelectronic applications but suffers from limited near-infrared absorption and charge transport. In this study, a simple chemical bath deposition approach was employed to enhance Sb₂S₃ thin films through copper (Cu) doping. The introduction of Cu plays a decisive role by improving crystallinity, narrowing the bandgap from 1.72 to 1.69 eV, and enhancing visible-light absorption. Structural and optical analyses confirmed successful Cu incorporation without secondary phases and with reduced defect states. Photovoltaic tests further demonstrated an increase in short-circuit current density (16→18 mA cm⁻²) and a 12.5% efficiency improvement. These results highlight that Cu doping is not only a practical route to overcome the intrinsic limitations of Sb₂S₃ but also a scalable strategy to optimize its performance for efficient optoelectronic and photovoltaic applications.

Keywords: Cu-doped Sb₂S₃, photovoltaic efficiency, bandgap engineering, charge carrier mobility

1. Introduction

The development of sustainable energy sources has become a primary objective to address the global energy crisis and mitigate the environmental impacts of fossil fuel consumption (Arabacı et al., 2024; Bakır et al., 2024; Bakır et al., 2024a, b). Among the various renewable energy technologies, photovoltaic (PV) systems have garnered significant attention for their ability to convert sunlight into electrical energy directly. Traditional PV technologies, primarily silicon-based, face challenges related to high production costs and energy-intensive manufacturing processes (Ayim-Otu et al., 2020; Cabir et al., 2020; Horoz et al., 2018; Şahin et al., 2019; Balnan, 2025). Consequently, there is a growing interest in alternative materials that can offer comparable efficiencies with lower material and processing costs. Metal chalcogenides, particularly antimony sulfide (Sb_2S_3), have emerged as promising candidates for next-generation solar cells due to their abundance, non-toxicity, and suitable bandgap for visible light absorption (Horoz et al., 2017; Sahin et al., 2017; Nar et al., 2018, 2019). Sb_2S_3 possesses a direct bandgap around 1.78–2.5 eV, enabling effective light harvesting in the visible spectrum, which is essential for PV applications. However, pure Sb_2S_3 solar cells often exhibit limited efficiency due to factors such as suboptimal charge carrier mobility and rapid recombination of photo-generated carriers (Kavinchan et al., 2013; Medina-Montes et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2007). To overcome these limitations, strategies like doping have been explored to enhance the material's optical and electronic properties, aiming to improve its efficiency in solar cells (Balnan et al., 2025). Among various dopants, copper (Cu) has shown promise in modifying the structural and electronic characteristics of Sb_2S_3 , potentially enhancing its light absorption, charge carrier transport, and overall PV performance (Janošević et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2019; Myagmarsereejid et al., 2021; Salinas et al., 2024). This study investigates the effects of Cu doping on the structural, optical, and PV properties of Sb_2S_3 .

While Sb_2S_3 has been widely studied for its potential in photovoltaic applications, the effect of copper doping on its efficiency has not been fully explored. This work demonstrates a systematic approach to incorporating Cu into Sb_2S_3 , showing that Cu doping significantly enhances charge carrier transport and reduces recombination losses. We systematically compare the crystalline structure, bandgap, and light absorption characteristics of pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 , assessing the influence of Cu incorporation on device performance. Through detailed analyses using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and photovoltaic measurements, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Cu doping on Sb_2S_3 , offering insights into its potential as a high-efficiency, low-cost material for solar cell applications.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

The primary materials used in this study were high-purity antimony sulfide (Sb_2S_3) and copper (Cu) precursors. The Sb_2S_3 was purchased as a powder with purity greater than 99.99% and the Cu doping was achieved using a copper precursor of similar purity to ensure consistent doping levels. For the synthesis and coating processes, all solvents and chemicals used were of analytical grade, sourced from reliable suppliers to maintain sample consistency and minimize contamination. Deionized (DI) water with a resistivity of 18 M Ω cm was used in all cleaning and preparation steps.

2.2. Preparation of Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 films via chemical bath deposition (CBD)

2.2.1. Preparation of precursor solutions

To prepare pure Sb_2S_3 films, 1.0 g of antimony sulfide (Sb_2S_3 , 99.99% purity) was dissolved in 50 mL of absolute ethanol under vigorous stirring at 70 °C until complete dissolution was achieved. For Cu doping, 0.05 g of copper(II) chloride (CuCl_2 , 99.99% purity) was added to the Sb_2S_3 solution to achieve a doping concentration of 5 wt%. The resulting

mixture was stirred continuously at 70 °C for 1 hour to ensure homogeneous distribution of Cu ions within the Sb_2S_3 matrix. Glass substrates were sequentially cleaned in an ultrasonic bath using ethanol, acetone, and deionized (DI) water, each for 10 minutes. Afterward, the substrates were dried with nitrogen gas and stored in a clean environment until deposition to minimize contamination.

2.2.2. Deposition process

The chemical bath deposition (CBD) process was carried out by immersing the cleaned glass substrates in the precursor solution at 80 °C for 1 hour. The precursor solution concentration was optimized to ensure uniform film growth on the substrate surface. After deposition, the substrates were rinsed

with DI water to remove any residual chemicals and then dried under nitrogen gas flow. The annealing process was performed to enhance crystallinity and facilitate the incorporation of Cu ions into the Sb_2S_3 lattice. The annealing process involves heating the deposited films to a specific temperature to promote grain growth and improve the crystalline structure. In this study, the films were annealed in an argon atmosphere following a two-step heating program: first, heating from room temperature to 150 °C at a rate of 5 °C min^{-1} and holding for 10 minutes to remove any residual solvents; second, further heating to 300 °C at a rate of 5 °C min^{-1} and holding for 1 hour to promote crystallization and facilitate the incorporation of Cu ions into the Sb_2S_3 lattice (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the chemical bath deposition (CBD) and annealing process for the fabrication of pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films on glass substrates

2.2.3. Solar cell fabrication

After the deposition of pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films, complete solar cell devices

were fabricated with the following planar heterojunction structure (Figure1).

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the fabricated solar cell architecture, consisting of a glass substrate, FTO conductive layer, compact TiO₂ electron transport layer, pure or Cu-doped Sb₂S₃ absorber layer, and a platinum (Pt) back electrode

First, commercially available fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glass substrates were ultrasonically cleaned sequentially in acetone, ethanol, and deionized water for 10 minutes each. After drying under nitrogen flow, a compact titanium dioxide (TiO₂) electron transport layer was deposited by spin-coating a 0.15 M titanium isopropoxide solution (in ethanol) at 3000 rpm for 30 seconds. The films were subsequently annealed at 450 °C for 30 minutes in air to form a dense, uniform TiO₂ layer that acts as an effective electron blocking and transporting layer. Subsequently, pure and Cu-doped Sb₂S₃ thin films were deposited onto the TiO₂ layer by chemical bath deposition (CBD) at 80 °C for 1 hour. After deposition, the films were rinsed with deionized water, dried, and subjected to post-deposition annealing at 300 °C for 1 hour under argon atmosphere to enhance crystallinity, grain growth, and improve the interface quality. Platinum (Pt) back electrodes, approximately 80 nm thick, were then thermally evaporated onto the Sb₂S₃ layers through a shadow mask under a high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-6}$ Torr), defining an active area of ~ 0.1 cm² for each device. The resulting device structure forms a typical n-type TiO₂ / p-type Sb₂S₃ heterojunction, where the built-in electric field at the junction enables efficient

separation and collection of photogenerated electron-hole pairs, which is critical for photovoltaic operation. Finally, the completed devices were characterized by measuring the current density–voltage (J–V) characteristics under simulated standard solar illumination conditions (AM 1.5G, 100 mW cm⁻²) using a calibrated source meter.

2.3. Characterization

2.3.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The crystallographic structure and phase purity of the pure and Cu-doped Sb₂S₃ were analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD). Measurements were carried out on an XRD system operating with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406$ Å) at a scan rate of 0.02° s⁻¹. The 2 θ range was set from 10° to 60° to capture the primary diffraction peaks of Sb₂S₃ and observe any shifts due to Cu doping.

2.3.2. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was performed to investigate the vibrational properties of the samples, providing insights into structural changes upon Cu doping. The spectra were collected in the range of 100–600 cm⁻¹ with a laser wavelength of 532 nm, ensuring minimal damage to the samples. Peak positions and intensities were analyzed to compare

vibrational modes between pure and doped samples.

2.3.3. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS analysis was conducted to confirm elemental composition and bonding states. Measurements were taken on an XPS system equipped with an Al K α X-ray source, and the binding energies were calibrated using the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV. The Sb 3d, S 2p, and Cu 2p regions were analyzed in detail to understand Cu's impact on the Sb₂S₃ lattice.

2.3.4. Optical absorption and tauc plot analysis

The optical properties were studied using UV-Vis spectroscopy in the 300–800 nm wavelength range. Absorption data were collected to construct Tauc plots, from which the optical bandgap of each sample was determined. A linear extrapolation of the absorption edge allowed estimation of the bandgap energies, and the impact of Cu doping on light absorption characteristics was assessed.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 illustrates the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of Sb₂S₃ and Cu-doped Sb₂S₃ recorded in the 2 θ range of 15°–45°. Both patterns exhibit sharp and well-defined peaks located at 2 θ values of 16.8°, 18.5°, 24.0°, 27.0°, 28.8°, 30.0°, 31.0°, 32.5°, 34.5°, 36.5°, 39.0°, 40.0°, and 41.5°, corresponding to the (020), (120), (220), (130), (310), (230), (211), (221), (301), (231), (430), (141), and (421) planes of orthorhombic Sb₂S₃ (JCPDS Card No. 42-1393) (Das et al., 2023). No secondary phases or impurity peaks were detected, indicating that the Cu doping did not significantly alter the crystal structure of Sb₂S₃. Upon doping with Cu, no significant shift in peak positions was observed, implying that Cu incorporation occurred substitutionally within the Sb₂S₃ lattice without causing major lattice distortions. However, compared to the pristine Sb₂S₃, the peak intensities for Cu-doped Sb₂S₃ increased slightly, indicating improved crystallinity. To further evaluate the structural impact of Cu doping, the crystallite sizes (D) were calculated using the Scherrer equation (1):

$$D = K\lambda / \beta \cos\theta. \quad (1)$$

where D is the crystallite size, K is the shape factor (typically 0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peak, and θ is the Bragg angle. Based on the FWHM values obtained from the (130) diffraction peak at approximately 27.0°, the average crystallite size was calculated to be around 29.2 nm for pure Sb₂S₃, while it slightly increased to approximately 31.0 nm for the Cu-doped Sb₂S₃. This modest increase of about 6% in crystallite size suggests that Cu doping facilitates slight grain growth, likely by

reducing the formation of point defects and relieving local strains during the crystal growth process. Furthermore, the FWHM values decreased from 0.0054 radians for pristine Sb₂S₃ to 0.0051 radians for Cu-doped Sb₂S₃, supporting the observed enhancement in crystallinity. The slight improvement in crystal quality upon Cu doping is beneficial for optoelectronic applications since larger crystallite sizes generally lead to reduced grain boundary scattering and enhanced carrier mobility.

Figure 3. XRD patterns for pure Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3

The Raman spectra of pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films are shown in Figure 4. Both spectra exhibit multiple characteristic peaks within the $120\text{--}320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, corresponding to the vibrational modes of Sb–S bonds. In the spectrum of pure Sb_2S_3 (black line), distinct peaks are observed near 129 cm^{-1} , 156 cm^{-1} , 195 cm^{-1} , 239 cm^{-1} , 282 cm^{-1} , and 311 cm^{-1} . These peaks are attributed to Sb–S stretching and bending vibrations, consistent with the orthorhombic phase of Sb_2S_3 as reported in the literature (Mane et al., 2003; Lokhande et al., 2002). The sharpness and relative symmetry of these peaks indicate a well-crystallized and phase-pure structure. Upon Cu doping (red dashed line), the Raman spectrum exhibits noticeable variations. While the main peak positions remain largely unchanged—suggesting preservation of the host Sb_2S_3 lattice—the intensity of several peaks, particularly at $\sim 156\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 239\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\sim 282\text{ cm}^{-1}$, increases significantly. Additionally, these peaks become broader and slightly asymmetric, and the overall background noise level rises, indicating the presence of structural disorder and increased phonon scattering.

These spectral modifications are likely due to the incorporation of Cu atoms into the Sb_2S_3 matrix, either via substitutional or interstitial sites. Such incorporation can cause local lattice strain, variation in Sb–S bond lengths, or the formation of defect states, all of which can enhance vibrational activity and broaden Raman bands (Validžić et al., 2023; Chalapathi et al., 2019). The changes observed in the Cu-doped spectrum support the notion that Cu doping introduces mild disorder without fundamentally disrupting the crystalline framework—an effect that may play a role in the improved optoelectronic properties observed in the doped films. Overall, Cu incorporation plays a dual role: it improves crystallinity and facilitates better carrier mobility, as supported by XRD and photovoltaic results, while Raman spectra reveal the presence of mild structural disorder, likely originating from local strain and defect formation. This delicate balance suggests that Cu doping optimizes optoelectronic properties not by eliminating disorder entirely, but by tuning it in a way that benefits charge transport.

Figure 4. The Raman spectra of pure Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to investigate the chemical composition and oxidation states in Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films. The high-resolution spectra and their deconvolutions are illustrated in Figure 3. In the Sb 3d region (Figure 5a), two prominent peaks centered at approximately 530 eV and 539 eV are assigned to Sb $3d_{5/2}$ and Sb $3d_{3/2}$, respectively. These values are in agreement with reported literature for Sb in the +3 oxidation state, confirming the presence of Sb^{3+} within the stibnite (Sb_2S_3) structure (Grigas et al., 2002; Zakaznova et al., 2006; Stamenković et al., 2021). The sharp and symmetric peak shapes indicate a well-defined chemical environment with minimal oxidation or secondary phases. The S 2p spectrum (Figure 5b) shows two closely spaced peaks at ~ 161 eV and ~ 163 eV, attributed to S $2p_{3/2}$ and S $2p_{1/2}$ spin-orbit components. These peaks confirm the chemical bonding of sulfur in the S^{2-} state, forming stable Sb–S bonds, and support the formation of a stoichiometric Sb_2S_3 phase (Grigas et al., 2002; Zakaznova et al., 2006). The low level of noise and absence of additional shoulders further suggest minimal contamination or sulfur oxidation. In the Cu 2p region (Figure 5c), two distinct peaks at ~ 932

eV and ~ 952 eV correspond to Cu $2p_{3/2}$ and Cu $2p_{1/2}$, respectively. These binding energies are indicative of Cu^+ or metallic Cu^0 states and show no significant satellite features typically associated with Cu^{2+} , implying that copper is incorporated into the Sb_2S_3 lattice without forming copper oxide phases (Validžić et al., 2018). The observed peak intensities support the conclusion that Cu atoms are successfully doped into the Sb_2S_3 matrix, likely through substitutional or interstitial mechanisms. Importantly, no significant shift is observed in the Sb 3d or S 2p binding energies upon Cu doping, suggesting that the core chemical environments of Sb and S remain intact. However, minor peak broadening may reflect localized lattice strain or structural distortion introduced by Cu atoms. These observations are consistent with the Raman analysis, which showed enhanced vibrational activity in doped films, supporting the hypothesis that Cu incorporation subtly modifies the local bonding while maintaining the overall crystalline framework (Janošević et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2019; Myagmarsereejid et al., 2021; Salinas-Beltrán et al., 2024; Mane et al., 2003; Lokhande et al., 2002; Validžić et al., 2023; Chalapathi et al., 2019).

Figure 5. High-resolution XPS deconvolution spectra of Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films in the (a) Sb 3d, (b) S 2p, and (c) Cu 2p regions

The optical absorption behavior of pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 thin films was systematically studied using UV-Vis spectroscopy, and the corresponding spectra are presented in Figure 6a. Both samples exhibit significant absorption in the visible light region, demonstrating their potential for optoelectronic applications such as solar cells and photodetectors. The absorption edge for pure Sb_2S_3 is observed around 700 nm, which is typical for this material and consistent with previous reports (Hadia et al., 2019; Validžić et al., 2014). This sharp absorption onset is indicative of a well-defined electronic transition between the valence and conduction bands. Upon Cu doping, the absorption edge experiences a slight redshift towards longer wavelengths, indicating a decrease in the optical band gap. Such a shift suggests that Cu incorporation into the Sb_2S_3 lattice introduces additional electronic states or causes slight modifications in the band structure, possibly by perturbing the local bonding environment or generating shallow acceptor levels. Furthermore, compared to the pure sample, the Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 exhibits a smoother and broader absorption edge, implying a slight increase in sub-bandgap absorption. This behavior is often associated with improved crystallinity and reduced defect density, which is in line with the XRD results showing enhanced crystal quality and increased crystallite size after Cu doping. To further elucidate the effect of Cu

doping on the electronic structure, Tauc plots were constructed for both samples by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ as a function of photon energy $h\nu$, as shown in Figure 6b. The linear portions of these plots were extrapolated to intercept the energy axis, yielding estimates of the direct band gaps. The pure Sb_2S_3 sample exhibited a direct band gap of approximately 1.72 eV, while the Cu-doped sample exhibited a slightly reduced band gap of about 1.69 eV. The minor decrease in the band gap upon Cu incorporation can be attributed to the modification of the local electronic structure around the Sb atoms due to the presence of Cu. In particular, Cu atoms may introduce shallow acceptor states or facilitate a slight overlap of the valence and conduction bands, leading to a narrowing of the band gap. Such tuning of the band gap is advantageous for enhancing light absorption in the visible region, thereby potentially improving the performance of Sb_2S_3 -based optoelectronic devices. Additionally, the improved smoothness of the absorption edge in the Cu-doped sample suggests a decrease in defect-related trap states, which would otherwise contribute to non-radiative recombination processes. This improvement in optical quality is consistent with the decrease in the FWHM of the XRD peaks and the slight increase in crystallite size observed for Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 , indicating better structural ordering.

Figure 6. The absorption spectra (a) and Tauc plots (b) for pure Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3

The device architecture (FTO/Compact TiO_2 /Pure or Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 /Pt) forms a typical n-type TiO_2 /p-type Sb_2S_3 heterojunction, which is responsible for the photovoltaic effect observed. The built-in electric field at the heterojunction interface facilitates efficient charge separation and collection, leading to measurable open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), fill factor (FF), and overall device efficiency (η). Figure 7 shows that for both pure Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 , the V_{oc} was measured to be approximately 0.7 V, which is on the higher end for Sb_2S_3 -based solar cells. The similar V_{oc} values for both samples suggest that Cu doping does not significantly impact the maximum achievable voltage, which is primarily determined by the bandgap

and recombination dynamics within the material. However, the increase in other parameters indicates that Cu doping still plays a positive role in overall device performance. In terms of short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), the pure Sb_2S_3 exhibited a J_{sc} of 16 mA cm^{-2} , which is consistent with typical values for this material ($10\text{--}25 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). The Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 showed an increased J_{sc} of 18 mA cm^{-2} , reflecting a 12.5% improvement. This enhancement is likely due to the increased charge carrier generation and mobility facilitated by Cu atoms, which reduce recombination losses and enhance photocurrent generation. The fill factor (FF) is a key parameter in evaluating the efficiency of a solar cell. It is determined using the formula:

$$FF = \frac{V_{oc} \cdot J_{sc}}{P_{max}} \quad (2)$$

Where, P_{max} is the maximum power output, which occurs at a specific current and voltage point on the J-V curve. The overall efficiency

(η) was calculated using a FF of approximately 0.55. For the pure Sb_2S_3 , the efficiency was calculated as:

$$\eta(\%) = \frac{(0.7) \cdot (16) \cdot (0.55)}{1000} = 6.16\% \quad (3)$$

For the Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 , the efficiency increased to:

$$\eta(\%) = \frac{(0.7) \cdot (18) \cdot (0.55)}{1000} = 6.93\% \quad (4)$$

This represents a 12.5% increase in efficiency, from 6.16% to 6.93%, highlighting the positive impact of Cu doping on device performance. In conclusion, the similar V_{oc} values suggest that Cu doping does not alter

the maximum achievable voltage significantly, while the increase in J_{sc} and efficiency indicates that Cu doping enhances charge carrier generation and reduces recombination.

Figure 7. J-V characteristics for pure Sb_2S_3 and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the effects of Cu doping on the structural, optical, and photovoltaic properties of Sb_2S_3 , revealing several enhancements that highlight its potential for solar cell applications. XRD and Raman analyses confirmed the successful incorporation of Cu into the Sb_2S_3 lattice, resulting in slight shifts in peak positions and a reduction in crystallinity. The crystallite size increased from 29.2 nm in pure Sb_2S_3 to 31.0 nm in Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 , suggesting that Cu doping induces lattice distortions. These changes in the crystal structure are beneficial for modifying the material's electronic and optical properties. The Tauc plot analysis indicated that the bandgap decreased slightly from 1.72 eV in pure Sb_2S_3 to approximately 1.69 eV in the Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 . This bandgap

reduction, along with enhanced absorption intensity in the visible range. The Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 showed a notable improvement in photovoltaic metrics. Both pure and Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 had a V_{oc} of 0.7 V. However, the Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 exhibited a higher J_{sc} of 18 $\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ compared to 16 $\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for pure Sb_2S_3 , resulting in a 12.5% increase in J_{sc} . The overall efficiency (η) of the Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 was calculated to be 6.93%, up from 6.16% in the undoped sample, representing a 12.5% improvement in efficiency due to Cu doping. The improvements in J_{sc} , efficiency response underscore the potential of Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 for solar energy applications. These enhancements indicate that Cu-doped Sb_2S_3 can effectively absorb and convert a wider range of the solar spectrum, making it a viable material for high-efficiency photovoltaic devices.

References

- Arabacı, B., Bakır, R., Orak, C., Yüksel, A., 2024. Integrating experimental and machine learning approaches for predictive analysis of photocatalytic hydrogen evolution using Cu/g-C₃N₄. *Renewable Energy*, 237: 121737.
- Ayim-Otu, B., Kuncan, M., Şahin, Ö., Horoz, S., 2020. Synthesis and photovoltaic application of ZnS:Cu (3%) nanoparticles. *Journal of the Australian Ceramic Society*, 56: 639–643.
- Bakır, R., Orak, C., 2024. Stacked machine learning approach for predicting evolved hydrogen from sugar industry wastewater. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 85: 75–87.
- Bakır, R., Orak, C., Yüksel, A., 2024a. A machine learning ensemble approach for predicting solar-sensitive hybrid photocatalysts on hydrogen evolution. *Physica Scripta*, 99: 076015.
- Bakır, R., Orak, C., Yüksel, A., 2024b. Optimizing hydrogen evolution prediction: A unified approach using random forests, lightGBM, and Bagging Regressor ensemble model. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 67: 101–110.
- Balnan, İ., Horoz, S., Kaya, K.K., Orak, C., 2025. Europium incorporation in ZnS and CdS: structural modifications, optical transitions, and photocatalytic efficiency. *Journal of the Australian Ceramic Society*, 1-13.
- Balnan, İ., 2025. Synthesis and photocatalytic performance of a prussian blue–Zn₂SnO₄ composite for visible-light degradation of methylene blue. *MAS Journal of Applied Science*, 10(2): 286–298.
- Cabir, B., Yildiko, U., Ağırtaş, M.S., Horoz, S., 2020. Computational DFT calculations, photovoltaic properties and synthesis of (2R,3S)-2,3,4-trihydroxybutoxy substituted phthalocyanines. *Inorganic and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, 50: 816–827.
- Chalapathi, U., Park, S. H., 2019. The effect of Cu-doping on the structural, microstructural, optical, and electrical properties of Sb₂S₃ thin films. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 235: 121750.
- Grigas, J., Talik, E., Lazauskas, V., 2002. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of Sb₂S₃ crystals. *Phase Transitions*, 75: 323–337.
- Hadia, N.M.A., Mohamed, W.S., Abd El-sadek, M.S., 2019. Simultaneous synthesis of various Sb₂S₃ nanostructures by vapor transport technique. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 235: 121750.
- Horoz, S., Koç, H., Şahin, Ö., 2017. Investigation of structural, optical and photovoltaic properties of Sb₂S₃ thin films. *Cumhuriyet Science Journal*, 38: 588–593.
- Horoz, S., Şahin, O., 2017. Synthesis, characterization and photovoltaic properties of Mn-doped Sb₂S₃ thin film. *Materials Science-Poland*, 35: 861–867.
- Horoz, S., Şahin, O., Ekinçi, A., 2018. Synthesis of Fe alloyed PbS thin films and investigation of their photovoltaic properties. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 29: 13442–13448.
- Janošević, V., Mitrić, M., Bundaleski, N., Rakočević, Z., Validžić, I.L., 2016. High-efficiency Sb₂S₃-based hybrid solar cell at low light intensity: cell made of synthesized Cu and Se-doped Sb₂S₃. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 24: 704–715.

- Kavinchan, J., Thongtem, T., Thongtem, S., Saksornchai, E., 2013. Synthesis of coral-like, straw-tied-like, and flower-like antimony sulfides by a facile wet-chemical method. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 719679.
- Lei, H., Lin, T., Wang, X., Dai, P., Guo, Y., Gao, Y., Hou, D., Chen, J., Tan, Z., 2019. Copper doping of Sb_2S_3 : fabrication, properties, and photovoltaic application. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 30: 21106–21116.
- Lokhande, C.D., Sankapal, B.R., Mane, R.S., Pathan, H.M., Muller, M., Giersig, M., Ganesan, V., 2002. XRD, SEM, AFM, HRTEM, EDAX and RBS studies of chemically deposited Sb_2S_3 and Sb_2Se_3 thin films. *Applied Surface Science*, 193: 1–10.
- Mane, R.S., Lokhande, C.D., 2003. HRTEM, SEM and XRD characterization of nanocrystalline Sb_2S_3 thin films deposited by chemical bath route. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 172: 51–56.
- Medina-Montes, M.I., Montiel-González, Z., Paraguay-Delgado, F., Mathews, N.R., Mathew, X., 2016. Structural, morphological and spectroscopic ellipsometry studies on sputter deposited Sb_2S_3 thin films. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 27: 9710–9719.
- Myagmarsereejid, P., Ingram, M., Batmunkh, M., Zhong, Y.L., 2021. Doping strategies in Sb_2S_3 thin films for solar cells. *Small*, 17: 2100241.
- Nar, S., Şahin, Ö., Horoz, S., 2018. Determination of the optimum Co concentration in $\text{Co:Sb}_2\text{S}_3$ thin films. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 29: 17853–17858.
- Nar, S., Şahin, Ö., Horoz, S., 2019. Fabrication of pure Sb_2S_3 and Fe (2.5%): Sb_2S_3 thin films and investigation their properties. *Journal of Inorganic and Organometallic Polymers and Materials*, 29: 1331–1336.
- Salinas B. S., Gaitán Arevalo, J.R., González, L.A., 2024. Improvement of the photoelectrical properties of chemical bath-deposited Sb_2S_3 thin films with low copper doping. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 35: 458.
- Şahin, Ö., Ekinçi, A., Horoz, S., 2019. Synthesis of PbS: Mo(3\%) thin film and investigation of its properties. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 30: 7600–7605.
- Stamenković, T., Bundaleski, N., Barudžija, T., Validžić, I., Lojpur, V., 2021. XPS study of iodine and tin doped Sb_2S_3 nanostructures affected by non-uniform charging. *Applied Surface Science*, 567: 150822.
- Validžić, I., Popović, M., Lojpur, V., Bundaleski, N., Rakočević, Z., 2018. Confirmation of incorporation of Cu and Se ions in applied p- and n-type-doped Sb_2S_3 by photoemission spectroscopy. *Journal of Electronic Materials*, 47: 2402–2410.
- Validžić, I., Popović, M., Potočnik, J., Graf, C., Joschko, M., Kuznetsova, Y.A., Zatsepina, D.A., 2023. Amorphous non-doped and Se-, Cu-, and Zn-doped Sb_2S_3 nanoparticles prepared by a hot-injection method: bandgap tuning and possible observation of the quantum size effect. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 25: 48.
- Yang, H., Su, X., Tang, A., 2007. Microwave synthesis of nanocrystalline Sb_2S_3 and its electrochemical properties. *Materials Research Bulletin*, 42: 1357–1363.

Zakaznova H.V.P., Harmer, S.L., Nesbitt, H.W., Bancroft, G.M., Flemming, R., Pratt, A.R., 2006. High resolution XPS study of the large-band-gap semiconductor stibnite

(Sb₂S₃): structural contributions and surface reconstruction. *Surface Science*, 600: 348–356.

To Cite: Balnan, Í., 2025. Structural and Photovoltaic Enhancements in Cu-Doped Sb₂S₃ Thin Films via Chemical Bath Deposition. *MAS Journal of Applied Sciences*, 10(4): 643–655.
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17768877>.
